

OCLC27258558

APPENDIX 3

**PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS
IN LAKE ERIE TRIBUTARIES**

1987

Submitted in partial fulfillment
of Grant R005967-01
from the
Great Lakes National Program Office
U. S. Environmental Protection Agency, Region V
Chicago, Illinois 60604

Robert Beltran, Project Officer

April 1989

DISCLAIMER

This project has been funded in part by the United States Environmental Protection Agency under assistance agreement R005967-01 to Heidelberg College. The contents of this report have not been reviewed by the Environmental Protection Agency and do not necessarily reflect the views and policies of the Environmental Protection Agency, nor does mention of trade names or commercial products constitute endorsement or recommendation for use.

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Support for these studies has come from many sources. Major support was provided by the U.S. EPA's Great Lakes National Program Office under assistance agreement R005967-01. The help of our project officer, Mr. Robert Beltran, is greatly appreciated. Matching funds for the EPA grants were provided by the following companies or organizations:

American Cyanamid
Ciba-Geigy Corporation
Dow Chemical Company
Monsanto Agricultural Products Company
Procter and Gamble Company
Rhône Poulenc, Inc.

Several organizations supported special aspects of these studies. Support for the Lost Creek Watershed study was provided by the U.S. Soil Conservation Service.

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Introduction

The data tables which follow contain the analytical results from the pesticide monitoring programs conducted by the Heidelberg College Water Quality Laboratory in 1987. These tables comprise Appendix 3 to our 1987 water year report to the U.S. EPA's Great Lakes National Program Office. The tables include data on those pesticides which we are able to detect most frequently in river samples. Tables similar to the above for our 1983-1986 pesticide monitoring programs are also available upon request.

The pesticide concentrations included in the tables are based on analyses using dual-column capillary gas chromatography and nitrogen-phosphorus thermionic specific detectors. The use of two different columns (Durabond-5 and Durabond-1) allowed simultaneous confirmation of concentrations for 10 of the 11 compounds reported. The analytical procedures used in these studies have been previously described (Kramer, J.W. and Baker, D.B. "An Analytical Method and Quality Control Program for Studies of Currently Used Pesticides in Surface Waters." Quality Assurance for Environmental Measurements, ASTM STP 867, J.K. Taylor and T.W. Stanley, Eds., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1985, pp. 116-132.) The analytical method is very similar to the U.S. EPA's Draft Method 507 (ORD, EMSL, Cincinnati, Ohio).

For each pesticide, the concentrations which are reported are from the column which provided the best combination of percent recovery (based on spiked samples) and precision (based on replicate samples). The columns used for each pesticide, along with the percent recovery and the detection limit are shown below. The reported concentrations have been corrected for recoveries less than 100%, using the average recoveries for that compound. Detection limits are based on analyses of dilution series of standards. A blank space in the data table indicates that the gas chromatograph had no machine response at the retention time for that particular pesticide and, consequently, that the pesticide concentration is below the method detection limit.

Pesticide	Column	Detection Limit ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Mean Percent Recovery
Alachlor	DB-1	0.10	74%
Atrazine	DB-1	0.05	76%
Cyanazine	DB-5	0.25	62%
Butylate	DB-1		61%
Metolachlor	DB-1	0.25	77%
Metribuzin	DB-1	0.10	70%
Pendimethalin	DB-5	0.05	71%
Simazine	DB-5	0.25	89%
Fonofos	DB-5	0.05	62%
Terbufos	DB-1	0.10	73%
Chlorpyrifos	DB-1		82%
Treflan	DB-1		84%
EPTC	DB-1		61%
Phorate	DB-1		68%

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN THE MAUMEE RIVER AT BOWLING GREEN, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE UG/L	ALACHLOR UG/L	METOLACHLOR UG/L	METRIEBUZIN UG/L	BUTYLATE UG/L	TERBUFOS UG/L	CHLORPYRIFOS UG/L	TREFLAN UG/L	EPIC UG/L	PHORATE UG/L
88	870202	1320	.23									
98	870209	1430	.30									
102	870309	1450	.45									
114	870330	1440	1.83									
123	870406	1500	.43	.22	.70	.06	.08	.01	.07			.02
137	870420	1300	.33	2.14	1.33	.49			.09		.07	.01
189	870504	1530	4.37	3.49	2.36	.58	.08	.01				
201	870507	1300	10.79	1.96	4.23	.07			.06			
202	870511	1500	6.00	1.76	2.12	.07					.11	
220	870514	1300	5.94		2.30	.07						
267	870518	1500	7.13	1.03	2.91	.53					.06	
398	870521	0100	7.33	1.75	4.93	1.31						
399	870522	0100	7.31	3.55	5.60	2.11						
400	870523	0100	7.99	3.99	6.87	3.64						
401	870523	1300	9.04	4.46	7.39							
402	870524	0100	10.19	5.21	8.97	3.93						
403	870524	1300	9.88	5.79	9.35	4.10						
391	870526	1430	12.13	7.51	10.69	3.35						
393	870530	0100	12.41	7.66	13.71	3.32						
396	870531	0100	11.90	6.71	11.64	3.22			.09			
404	870601	1535	9.93	4.08	8.11	2.09			.05			
538	870604	1300	10.13	3.55	9.41	1.57						
539	870605	0100	11.74	3.77	10.70	1.73						
541	870608	1550	12.47	4.06	11.03	3.07			.06			
607	870609	1300	12.60	3.89	11.04	3.23						.02
608	870610	1300	12.89	4.06	11.61	2.96						
609	870611	1300	12.74	4.22	12.22	3.11						
610	870612	1300	13.05	4.26	12.67	3.04						
611	870613	1300	12.27	4.05	12.09	2.85						
612	870614	1300	11.17	4.10	12.00	2.98			.04			
604	870615	1400	8.63	1.71	7.99	1.43						
765	870618	1300	9.46	3.05	7.97	2.25			.07			
766	870622	1455	7.97	2.52	6.66	2.13						
822	870625	0100	7.08	1.99	5.43	1.34						
824	870628	0100	6.22	1.34	4.31	1.08						

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN THE MAUMEE RIVER AT BOWLING GREEN, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONOFOS UG/L	NOTES
88	870202	1320				1.14	
98	870209	1430			.01		
102	870309	1450				.10	
114	870330	1440	.04	.10	.06	.17	
123	870406	1500	.17	.11			
137	870420	1300	.04				
189	870504	1530	1.73	.09	.29	.53	
201	870507	1300	5.31		.31	1.50	
202	870511	1500	2.13	.07	1.41	.75	
220	870514	1300	1.73		.80	.57	
267	870518	1500	1.25	.07	.52	.93	
398	870521	0100	2.80	.02		.56	
399	870522	0100	3.22	.13		.78	
400	870523	0100	5.61	.13		.90	
401	870523	1300	5.85	.14		1.23	
3	402	870524	0100	6.15		1.49	
	403	870524	1300	6.03		1.44	
	391	870526	1430	7.31		1.77	
	393	870530	0100	6.83		2.01	
	396	870531	0100	6.36		1.63	
	404	870601	1535	4.38	.10	1.45	
	538	870604	1300	2.56	.14	1.40	
	539	870605	0100	2.52	.14	1.59	
	541	870608	1550	3.05	.22	1.77	
	607	870609	1300	3.14	.22	2.52	
	608	870610	1300	2.84	.24	2.67	
	609	870611	1300	2.86	.23	2.15	
	610	870612	1300	2.72	.24	1.99	
	611	870613	1300	2.39	.20	1.74	
	612	870614	1300	1.81	.19	1.28	
	604	870615	1400	.18			SPIKE 0X1
	765	870618	1300	1.52	.19	1.32	.82
	766	870622	1455	1.28	.15	1.11	.55
	822	870625	0100	1.48	.23		
	824	870628	0100	1.07	.18	.56	

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN THE MAUMEE RIVER AT BOWLING GREEN, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE UG/L	ALACHLOR UG/L	METOLACHLOR UG/L	METRIBUZIN UG/L	BUTYLATE UG/L	TERBUFOS UG/L	CHLORPYRIFOS UG/L	TREFLAN UG/L	EPTC UG/L	PHORATE UG/L
838	870629	1415	4.73	.78	4.69	.85						
944	870702	1300	.18									
953	870706	1125	3.07	1.93	3.56	1.09						
1034	870710	0100	4.55	.98	4.17			.02				
1045	870713	1450	4.56	1.07	4.92	1.07			.04			
1083	870716	1300	3.97	.52	3.26	.59						
1092	870720	1500	3.32	.31	2.77	.55			.05			
1138	870727	1440	3.01	.32	2.40	.21						
1234	870810	1435	2.47		2.70	.03						
1262	870817	1440	2.07		1.03				.01			
1274	871005	1500										
1293	871019		1.40	.54		.33			.11	.98		.02
1313	871102	1505	.82		.40				.04			
1320	871116	1445	.66		.45				.02			
1364	871130	1510	.80	.24	1.37				.05			
1390	871214	1405	.48		.37							
1151	87723	1300	3.31	.29	2.65	.42			.02			
1405	880111	1450	.44		.33							

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN THE MAUMEE RIVER AT BOWLING GREEN, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONOFOS UG/L	NOTES
838	870629	1415	.86	.14			SPIKE OX1
944	870702	1300					
953	870706	1125	.44				SPIKE OX1
1034	870710	0100			.03		
1045	870713	1450	.65	.35		.44	SPIKE OX1
1083	870716	1300	.55	.25	.43		
1092	870720	1500		.17			SPIKE OX1
1138	870727	1440	.45	.20	.03		SPIKE OX1
1234	870810	1435	.36		.24		FIELD REP 0
1262	870817	1440	.36		.22		FIELD REP 0
1274	871005	1500					
1293	871019		.82	.13	.25	.07	
1313	871102	1505	.19				
1320	871116	1445	.12				
1364	871130	1510					
5 1390	871214	1405					
1151	87723	1300	1.29	.26	.31		
1405	880111	1450					

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN SANDUSKY RIVER AT FREMONT, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE UG/L	ALACHLOR UG/L	METOLACHLOR UG/L	METRIBUZIN UG/L	BUTYLATE UG/L	TERBUFOS UG/L	CHLORPYRIFOS UG/L	TREFLAN UG/L	EPTC UG/L	PHORATE UG/L
87	870126	1610	.36									
91	870202	1630										
103	870309	1610	.44									
116	870330	1540	.56	.25	.86	.05			.04			
124	870406	1645	.47	.28	.81	.19	.097	.03	.24	.12	.06	.04
134	870421	0900	.33		.37	.06			.07			.01
171	870504	1645	1.49	.71	.28	.14						
197	870511	1600	1.62	.34	1.37						.06	
219	870514	1300	1.05	.37	1.14							
256	870518	1605	1.06	.41	.74				.03			
392	870526	1555	21.64	13.18	26.12	5.79						.03
325	870527		11.81	11.91	14.62	4.27						.04
370	870601	1650	2.08	.81	.48	.15	.047		.08			.03
464	870603	0100	15.84	12.11	19.67	4.63						
465	870603	1300	15.73	7.90	16.93	4.54						
9	468	870604	0100	14.12	6.34	14.82	3.96		.06			
	469	870604	1300	15.40	7.03	12.04	3.27					
	470	870605	0100	15.32	7.66	10.17	3.25					
	471	870605	1300	11.51	4.15	10.12	2.33					
	472	870606	0100	11.35	3.53	10.56	1.64					
	473	870606	1300	12.96	3.09	11.45	2.01					
	475	870607	0100	12.71	3.09	11.34	2.34					
	466	870608	1600	12.56	2.89	10.60	1.67					
	618	870609	0100	12.87	3.83	10.30	2.13					
	619	870609	1300	11.36	3.50	9.07	1.75					
	620	870610	0100	12.74	4.49	10.31	2.17		.02			
	621	870610	1300	12.76	5.67	11.07	1.76					
	622	870611	0100	12.36	5.61	12.04	1.89					
	623	870611	1300	14.63	6.14	13.20	2.08					
	624	870612	0100	15.18	5.15	14.68	2.01					
	625	870612	1300	13.37	4.56	12.72	2.16		.03			

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN THE SANDUSKY RIVER AT FREMONT, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONOFOS UG/L	NOTES	
87	870126	1610				.85		
91	870202	1630				.98		
103	870309	1610						
116	870330	1540	.04		.01			
124	870406	1645	.13	.21	.68			
134	870421	0900	.14	.08				
171	870504	1645	.47		.14	.26		
197	870511	1600	.43		.10	.21		
219	870514	1300	.21		.08	.08		
256	870518	1605	.25		.08	.15	SPIKE OX1	
392	870526	1555	4.47	.67		3.49		
325	870527		1.93	.33	1.08	1.55	SPIKE OX1	
370	870601	1650	.65	.09	.91	.10		
464	870603	0100						
465	870603	1300						
7	468	870604	0100	2.53	.46	1.11	1.84	
469	870604	1300						
470	870605	0100	2.09	.21	.73			
471	870605	1300	1.84	.20	.96			
472	870606	0100						
473	870606	1300	1.69	.35	.85			
475	870607	0100		.36				
466	870608	1600	1.52	.34	.79	1.47	SPIKE OX1	
618	870609	0100	1.46	.21	.74	1.26		
619	870609	1300	1.76	.25	.80	1.76		
620	870610	0100	1.55	.31	.90	1.76		
621	870610	1300	1.18	.37	.67	1.95		
622	870611	0100	.84	.23	.35	1.87		
623	870611	1300	1.48	.33	.58	2.26		
624	870612	0100	1.39	.35	.91	2.20		
625	870612	1300	1.32	.32	.90	1.81		

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN SANDUSKY RIVER AT FREMONT, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE UG/L	ALACHLOR UG/L	METOLACHLOR UG/L	METRIBUZIN UG/L	BUTYLATE UG/L	TERBUFOS UG/L	CHLORPYRIFOS UG/L	TREFLAN UG/L	EPTC UG/L	PHORATE UG/L
626	870613	0100	12.64	4.08	11.88	1.64						
630	870613	1300	8.18	4.14	11.11	2.26			.06			
631	870614	0100	11.10	3.45	13.09	2.16						
627	870615	1325	9.66	3.31	9.74	1.55						
728	870616	0100	8.43	5.37	7.27	2.25			.04			
729	870616	1300	18.94	7.92	13.34	3.66			.08			
730	870617	0100	14.95	5.05	10.17	2.55			.02			
732	870617	1300	13.96	3.89	9.14	2.04			.02			
733	870618	1300		1.81	4.58				.03		.15	
734	870619	1300	11.78	2.73	8.00	1.46						
735	870620	1300	9.56	2.11	6.52	1.09						
825	870624	0100	8.95	3.10	5.76	1.58						
827	870626	0100	5.57	1.59	5.02	1.02			.05			
828	870628	0100	2.16	.31	.84	.15			.12			
861	870629	1430	4.75	1.14	4.87	.84						
∞ 933	870630	1300	5.55	.99	4.97	.93						.03
934	870701	1300	3.04	.79	3.09	.89						
935	870702	1300	3.98	.80	3.44	.72			.03			
937	870703	0100	4.03	1.20	4.02	.82			.05			
938	870703	1300	5.06	1.60	5.43	1.05						
940	870704	0100	2.95	.90	2.92	.65						
942	870705	0100	4.82	1.90	4.58	.83						
943	870705	1300	1.14	.25		.44						
930	870706	1450		1.08		.79						
1040	870710	0100	4.63	.78	4.09	.55			.03			

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CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONDFOS UG/L	NOTES
626	870613	0100	.99	.30	.76	1.98	
630	870613	1300	4.78	3.02	3.54	2.62	
631	870614	0100	1.27	.41	.77	1.58	
627	870615	1325	1.11	.23	.47	1.28	SPIKE 0X1
728	870616	0100	.81	.26	.60	.57	
729	870616	1300	1.14	.55	.93	1.82	
730	870617	0100	.93	.41	.67	1.71	
732	870617	1300	.98	.38	.57		
733	870618	1300		.21		2.55	
734	870619	1300	.78	.25	.56	1.01	
735	870620	1300	.76	.18	.42	1.03	
825	870624	0100	.62	.13	.88		
827	870626	0100	.43	.10			
828	870628	0100	.11		3.24		
861	870629	1430	.40	.08			SPIKE 0X1
933	870630	1300		.14			
934	870701	1300					
935	870702	1300					
937	870703	0100	.66				
938	870703	1300	.45				
940	870704	0100					
942	870705	0100	.40				
943	870705	1300					
930	870706	1450			1.78		SPIKE 0X1
1040	870710	0100	.41	.15			

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PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN SANDUSKY RIVER AT FREMONT, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE UG/L	ALACHLOR UG/L	METOLACHLOR UG/L	METRIBUZIN UG/L	BUTYLATE UG/L	TERBUFOS UG/L	CHLORPYRIFOS UG/L	TREFLAN UG/L	EPTC UG/L	PHORATE UG/L
1072	870715	1300	2.93	.44	2.72	.26						
1073	870716	0100	2.35	.79	3.10							
1074	870716	1300	3.53	.61	2.56	.27				.28		
1075	870717	0100	3.58	.51	3.04	.36						
1076	870717	1300	3.28	.51	2.82	.29						
1078	870718	1300	3.58	.49	2.93	.45			.03			
1082	870719	1300	3.76	.46	2.63	.37			.03			
1115	870720	1615	3.35	.33	2.27	.17			.05			
1150	870723	1300	2.47	.23	.88	.14			.03			
1161	870727	1605		.14			15.74			.16	.18	.16
1207	870803	1540	1.14		.69							
1372	871130	1610		.14	.42				.17			

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN THE SANDUSKY RIVER AT FREMONT, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONOFOS UG/L	NOTES
1072	870715	1300	.14	.10			
1073	870716	0100					
1074	870716	1300		.13	.15		
1075	870717	0100		.15			
1076	870717	1300		.21			
1078	870718	1300		.19			
1082	870719	1300		.14			
1115	870720	1615		.13			SPIKE 0X1
1150	870723	1300	.58				
1161	870727	1605	.41		.48		SPIKE 0X1
1207	870803	1540	.03				SPIKE 0X1
1372	871130	1610	.04				SPIKE 0X1

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN HONEY CREEK AT MELMORE, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE UG/L	ALACHLOR UG/L	METOLACHLOR UG/L	METRIBUZIN UG/L	BUTYLATE UG/L	TERBUFOS UG/L	CHLORPYRIFOS UG/L	TREFLAN UG/L	EPTC UG/L	PHORATE UG/L
86	870126	0900	.28									
93	870202	0930	.41		.51		.37				.14	
104	870309	0900										
115	870330	0930	.47	.26	.86							
119	870406	0930	.69	.40	.39	.16			.09			
136	870420	0910	.28	.16	.21							
172	870504	0945	1.31	.46	.99				.03			
205	870507	1900	1.72	.81	.89							
206	870511	0920	2.60	.88	2.13							
270	870514	1900	1.47	.32	1.01							
269	870518	0930	4.26	.33	3.07							
340	870520		46.20	74.14	30.86	7.04						.02
338	870520	0100	17.38	18.71	13.59	2.24						
339	870520	0700	34.09	69.91	19.97	5.79						
341	870520	1900	39.48	55.35	25.58	7.40						.02
343	870521	0100	33.79	47.08	23.64	6.14				.15		.03
344	870521	0700	29.73	36.52	20.81	5.24						.02
345	870522	0700	17.65	16.79	11.18	3.01						
346	870526	0840	6.53	3.54	4.26	1.01			.03			
373	870529	1900	14.73	8.21	6.71	1.33			.05			
374	870601	0945	8.46	2.37	10.68	.69						
519	870603	0100	14.27	3.36	19.72	2.65			.02		.08	
520	870603	0700	22.83	16.18	14.23	3.89				.23		
521	870603	1900	18.33	13.02	13.34	3.22						
523	870604	0700	22.80	12.39	10.93	1.74						.01
524	870604	1900	20.44	9.86	10.75	1.90				.24		
525	870605	0700	18.89	10.14	10.16	2.01						
526	870606	0700	17.31	7.06	8.43	2.00						
527	870607	0700	14.32	5.29	6.89	1.71				.22		
666	870608	0100	18.63	4.72	21.12	2.82			.03			.05
667	870608	0700	16.88	24.96	18.09	4.96				.26		.02
528	870608	0930	11.21	3.36	5.07	1.14						
668	870608	1300	17.99	10.60	13.58	2.35						
669	870608	1900	10.50	3.31	6.32	1.03						
670	870609	0100	18.31	20.77	10.40	1.93				.24		

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PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN HONEY CREEK AT MELMORE, OHIO IN 1987

21-JUL-1988
PAGE 1

CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONDFOS UG/L	NOTES
86	870126	0900			.02	.20	
93	870202	0930	.04				
104	870309	0900					
115	870330	0930	.03				
119	870406	0930	.10	.10	.11		
136	870420	0910					
172	870504	0945	.22		7.30		
205	870507	1900	.49				
206	870511	0920	1.01		.07	.24	
270	870514	1900	.69		.15	.38	
269	870518	0930	.39		.08	.25	
340	870520		23.76	.16	.06	.49	
338	870520	0100	4.81		1.17	9.14	
339	870520	0700	11.93	.13	.41	3.21	
341	870520	1900	.06	12.94	.98	6.71	
343	870521	0100	8.53		.54	.52	
344	870521	0700	7.71	.18	5.84	1.79	
345	870522	0700	3.29	.13	4.54	1.57	
346	870526	0840	1.88		3.63	.87	
373	870529	1900	1.90	.07	1.44	.27	
374	870601	0945	.96		3.49	.77	
519	870603	0100	2.24		.92	.39	
520	870603	0700	12.10	.04	.03		
521	870603	1900	5.61	.25	.18	2.73	
523	870604	0700	1.13		.18	3.58	
524	870604	1900	3.20	.15	.16	1.94	
525	870605	0700	4.26	.14	.30	3.17	
526	870606	0700	4.99	.16	.65	2.96	
527	870607	0700	4.83	.06	1.00	2.55	
666	870608	0100	4.32	.10	1.15	2.02	
667	870608	0700	2.62	.08	.58	2.85	
528	870608	0930	3.66	.08	.37	2.50	
668	870608	1300	3.65	.06	.63	1.65	
669	870608	1900	2.30	.14	.61	2.25	
670	870609	0100	1.72		.59	2.51	
					.43	4.42	

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PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN HONEY CREEK AT MELMORE, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE	ALACHLOR	METOLACHLOR	METRIBUZIN	BUTYLATE	TERBUFOS	CHLORPYRIFOS	TREFLAN	EPTC	PHORATE
			UG/L	UG/L	UG/L	UG/L	UG/L	UG/L	UG/L	UG/L	UG/L	UG/L
671	870609	0700	24.85	17.08	15.11	1.92						
673	870609	1300	25.46	15.62	14.51	2.25						
676	870609	1900	26.60	13.70	15.18	2.57			.10	.39		
677	870610	0100	24.97	12.64	12.60	2.27						
678	870610	0700	24.73	12.68	12.41	2.59						
679	870610	1300	24.68	12.20	12.39	2.52						
680	870610	1900	23.83	11.75	12.10	2.35						
681	870611	0100	21.44	9.86	10.63	2.20						.01
682	870611	0700	18.05	7.74	9.14	1.81						
687	870612	1300	17.57	6.71	8.49	1.98				.29		
688	870612	1900	17.45	7.15	8.80	1.69						
689	870613	0100	16.02	6.05	8.50	1.56						
690	870613	0700	16.63	5.39	12.94	1.91						
691	870613	1300	11.91	5.38	7.60	1.42						
692	870613	1900	11.69	3.95	6.16	1.19						
693	870614	0100	11.00	3.40	6.20	1.09						
695	870614	0700	11.15	3.54	7.66	1.18						
696	870614	1300	9.94	3.19	6.50	.94						
699	870614	1900	.01									
700	870615	0100	10.02	3.47	4.03	.98			.03			
701	870615	0700	10.15	3.21	4.15	.93						
702	870615	0900	9.58	3.22	4.13	.89			.03			
746	870621	0100	13.31	1.46	17.80	5.81		.01	.02			
747	870621	0700	9.61	5.29	10.59	3.15			.01			
748	870621	1300	7.27	2.42	4.66	.98						
750	870621	1900	11.71	3.02	6.95	1.10						
751	870622	0100	5.89	2.53	3.03	.59		.01	.01			.01
752	870622	0700	15.31	7.91	7.56	1.78			.03			
753	870622	0930	14.69	6.86	7.93	2.02			.01			
849	870622	1300	11.00	5.64	5.98	1.29			.01			
850	870622	1900	11.16	4.72	5.49	.94						
851	870623	0100	11.50	3.86	6.44	1.03						
852	870623	0700	15.64	5.74	10.07	1.72						
853	870623	1900	9.31	3.88	5.79	.92						
854	870624	0700	8.95	2.50	4.63	.88						

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PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN HONEY CREEK AT MELMORE, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONOFOS UG/L	NOTES
671	870609	0700	1.66	.06	.41	4.72	
673	870609	1300	4.12	.29	.50	3.28	
676	870609	1900	5.36	1.69	2.27	3.95	
677	870610	0100	3.43	.29	.58	4.80	
678	870610	0700	3.36	.29	.64	4.63	
679	870610	1300	3.34	.18	.71	4.61	
680	870610	1900	3.44	.16	.69	4.23	
681	870611	0100	3.26	.18	.69	3.70	
682	870611	0700	2.51	.18	.67	3.54	
687	870612	1300	2.17	.16	.60	2.65	
688	870612	1900	2.25	.14	.51	3.15	
689	870613	0100	2.22	.20	.54	2.92	
690	870613	0700	2.39	.12	.38	3.00	
691	870613	1300	1.79	.14	.48	2.12	
692	870613	1900	1.97	.09	.41	1.83	
15 693	870614	0100	1.87	.05	.37	1.63	
695	870614	0700	1.66	.07	.34	1.35	
696	870614	1300	1.63	.08	.37	1.71	
699	870614	1900					
700	870615	0100	1.48		.28	1.36	
701	870615	0700	1.55	.08	.29	1.39	
702	870615	0900	1.50	.09	.27	1.33	
746	870621	0100	3.08		.14	1.59	
747	870621	0700	1.85			1.12	
748	870621	1300	.78			.72	
750	870621	1900				1.73	
751	870622	0100	.76			.95	
752	870622	0700	2.15	.16	.37	2.18	
753	870622	0930	1.54	.21	.48	2.06	
849	870622	1300	1.45	.11	.19	1.22	
850	870622	1900	1.00	.09	.26	1.12	
851	870623	0100	1.19	.09	.21	.91	
852	870623	0700	1.28		.58	1.55	
853	870623	1900	.66				
854	870624	0700	.54			.84	

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN HONEY CREEK AT MELMORE, OHIO IN 1987

20-JUL-1988
PAGE 3

CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE UG/L	ALACHLOR UG/L	METOLACHLOR UG/L	METRIBUZIN UG/L	BUTYLATE UG/L	TERBUFOS UG/L	CHLORPYRIFOS UG/L	TREFLAN UG/L	EPTC UG/L	PHORATE UG/L
855	870624	1900	8.33	3.34	4.21	.63						
856	870625	1900	6.96	1.84	4.07	.77						
857	870626	1900	5.82	1.08	3.81	.54						
858	870628	1900	4.70	1.03	1.87	.42						
864	870629	0905	4.64	1.27	2.20	.55						
946	870702	1300	4.93	1.56	4.63	.51						
948	870702	1900	7.41	4.97	4.13	.68						
949	870703	0100	8.08	3.12	3.80	.68						
950	870703	0700	7.05	1.67	2.78	.52						
951	870703	1300	7.40	1.45	3.19	.51						
952	870703	1900	7.35	1.19	3.19	.52						
955	870704	0100	7.38	1.54	3.61	.78		.02				
956	870704	0700	7.21	.75	3.46	.60						
957	870704	1900	7.71	1.34	4.13	.56						
959	870705	0700	8.22	.92	4.53	.58		.02				
960	870705	1300	7.95	.76	3.06	.58						
961	870705	1900	7.40	1.02	4.28	.50						
963	870706	0100	6.91	.76	3.33	.55						
964	870706	0700	6.62	.65	3.19	.50						
965	870706	0830	6.63	.85	2.93	.55						
1014	870706	1900		1.91		1.01					.24	
1015	870707	0700									.20	
1017	870713	0915	.08	.42	2.66							
1084	870714	1300	3.53	.39	2.57	.63						
1085	870715	0100	4.06	.25	.96			.02	.06			
1086	870715	0700	4.98	1.84	2.01							
1087	870715	1300	5.14	1.23	2.26	.34						
1088	870716	0100	5.09	.93	2.28	.32						
1089	870716	1300	4.89	.70	2.28	.34						
1091	870720	0945	2.98	.19	1.56	.24			.04			
1152	870721	0700	3.26	.41	2.29	.44	.16	.04	.22	.25		.03
1153	870725	0100	2.81	.55	1.40							
1154	870727	0855	2.28	.55	1.01	.16			.06	.12		.01

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PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN HONEY CREEK AT MELMORE, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONDFOS UG/L	NOTES
855	870624	1900	.47			.61	
856	870625	1900	.37				
857	870626	1900					
858	870628	1900	.53		.01		
864	870629	0905	.71				
946	870702	1300	1.23				
948	870702	1900	3.04		.45		
949	870703	0100	1.78				
950	870703	0700	.94				
951	870703	1300	.81				
952	870703	1900	.94				
955	870704	0100	1.46				
956	870704	0700	.83				
957	870704	1900	.85		.39		
959	870705	0700	.90		.32		
17 960	870705	1300	1.02		.32		
961	870705	1900	.95				
963	870706	0100	.82				
964	870706	0700	.84				
965	870706	0830	.85				
1014	870706	1900	.08				
1015	870707	0700	.09				
1017	870713	0915		.03	.01		
1084	870714	1300	.83	.18	.37		
1085	870715	0100			.55		
1086	870715	0700					
1087	870715	1300	1.53	.12	.27		
1088	870716	0100	1.52	.14			
1089	870716	1300					
1091	870720	0945	.40	.20			
1152	870721	0700	.60	.57			
1153	870725	0100					
1154	870727	0855	.34	.12			

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN HONEY CREEK AT MELMORE, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE UG/L	ALACHLOR UG/L	METOLACHLOR UG/L	METRIBUZIN UG/L	BUTYLATE UG/L	TERBUFOS UG/L	CHLORPYRIFOS UG/L	TREFLAN UG/L	EPTC UG/L	PHORATE UG/L
1187	870803	0900	3.84	.10	4.12	.19						
1228	870804	0920	2.75	.65	1.16	.43				.39		.03
1227	870806	1900	2.25	.25	.55							
1276	871005	0930	.30									
1294	871019		6.69		.74				.04			
1317	871102	0925	.97	.15	1.22							
1363	871130	0925	2.43	.25	2.80							
1391	871214	1530	1.89	.62	.65				.03			
1403	880111	0920	.33		.47							
1408	880125	0925	.85	.34	.42				.04			

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN HONEY CREEK AT MELMORE, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONDFOS UG/L	NOTES
1187	870803	0900	1.19	1.49	1.43		
1228	870804	0920	.48	.01			
1227	870806	1900	.51				
1276	871005	0930					
1294	871019		1.62			1.92	
1317	871102	0925	.27				
1363	871130	0925					
1391	871214	1530					
1403	880111	0920	.07				
1408	880125	0925	.06				

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN ROCK CREEK AT TIFFIN, OHIO IN 1987

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PAGE 1

CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE UG/L	ALACHLOR UG/L	METDACHLOR UG/L	METRIBUZIN UG/L	BUTYALTE UG/L	TERBUFOS UG/L	CHLORPYRIFOS UG/L	TREFLAN UG/L	EPTC UG/L	PHORATE UG/L
48	870126	0840	.06	.38	.39	.12	.39	.02	.03	.14	.43	.02
92	870202	0905	.16			.05						
94	870209	0840	.61									
105	870309	0850										
112	870330	0900	.13			.03			.04			
120	870406	0902	.72	.22	.30	.09	2.70		.04			
135	870420	0840	.17						.03			
140	870427	0840	.14						.03			
173	870504	0915	.37	.19	.21				.02			
203	870507	1900	1.36	.52	.41				.07			
204	870511	0845	1.03	.73	.27				.03			
266	870518	0845	.61	.43	.43	.05			.03			
336	870521	1900	1.83	.80	1.01	.16						
302	870525	1445	2.05	.53	1.01	.05			.03			
384	870530	1300	1.32	.35	1.81	.13						
385	870530	1900	1.04	.37	1.29				.12			
387	870531	0100	1.12	.45	2.23				.07			
388	870531	0700	1.02	.30	15.31	1.85						
389	870531	1300	1.37	.56	18.20	2.41						
417	870601	0900	6.61	1.67	14.90	1.79						.02
506	870602	1900	.25									
508	870603	0100	9.67	2.24	11.08	1.74			.06			
509	870603	0700	17.51	22.82	10.42	6.30			.03			
510	870603	1300	22.79	16.86	24.23	5.20			.04			
511	870603	1900	17.05	8.95	19.94	4.94			.04			.02
514	870604	0700	16.14	7.63	18.04	4.05			.10			.05
515	870604	1900	14.32	7.87	15.42	3.05			.04			.02
516	870606	0700	8.05	2.52	9.86	1.43						
517	870608	0835	6.55	1.22	7.56	.88			.03			
589	870613	1900	3.62	.60	4.61	.33			.07			
590	870614	0100	4.30	.98	6.18	.60			.05			
592	870614	0700	7.89	1.58	5.89	.78			.02			
593	870614	1300	6.37	1.62	5.58	.80						
594	870615	0100	5.75	1.86	6.17	1.03			.05			
558	870615	0830	5.40	2.59	5.44	.86			.05			

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PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN ROCK CREEK AT TIFFIN, OHIO IN 1987

21-JUL-1988
PAGE 1

CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONOFOS UG/L	NOTES
48	870126	0840	6.96	4.98	3.81	.61	SPIKE OX1
92	870202	0905	.02				
94	870209	0840					SPIKE OX1
105	870309	0850					
112	870330	0900	.05	.05	.02		
120	870406	0902	.03		.04		FIELD REP 0
135	870420	0840			.20		
140	870427	0840			.52		SPIKE OX1
173	870504	0915			.08		SPLIT 0
203	870507	1900			.09		
204	870511	0845			.03		
266	870518	0845	.17		.09		
336	870521	1900	.17		.07		
302	870525	1445	.04		.03		SPIKE OX1
384	870530	1300					
21	385	870530		.11	44.58	.03	
	387	870531	.24		1.43	5.39	
	388	870531			1.89		
	389	870531				40.07	
	417	870601	.53	.19		1.31	SPIKE OX1
506	870602	1900	.32		3.50	3.14	
508	870603	0100	.48		.42		
509	870603	0700	2.80			2.12	
510	870603	1300	5.27	.06		3.54	
511	870603	1900	3.01	.10	.05	2.85	
514	870604	0700	4.67	2.61	3.38	2.30	
515	870604	1900	1.21	.20		2.53	
516	870606	0700	.82		.03	1.77	
517	870608	0835	.23			.87	
589	870613	1900	.97	.11			
590	870614	0100	.36			.27	
592	870614	0700					
593	870614	1300	.31			.85	
594	870615	0100	.26			.86	
558	870615	0830					SPIKE OX1

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN ROCK CREEK AT TIFFIN, OHIO IN 1987

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PAGE 2

CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONOFOS UG/L	NOTES
741	870621	0700					
742	870622	0905					FIELD REF 0
831	870626	0700	.25			.56	
832	870626	1300	.28				
833	870626	1900	.82				
834	870627	0100	.69				
919	870702	1900					
920	870703	1900					
921	870704	0700					
922	870704	1300					
923	870704	1900					
924	870705	0100					
926	870705	0700			4.14		
927	870705	1300	.02		1.60		
928	870705	1900	.04				
23 929	870706	0100					
932	870706	0700	.01				
907	870706	1520	.02				SPIKE 0X1
1003	870706	1900	.20				
1004	870707	0100		.20			
1005	870707	0700	.05				
1006	870707	1300	.06				
1007	870707	1900	.13				
1009	870708	0700	.05	.29			
1010	870708	1900					
1011	870709	0700					
1012	870710	0700	.04				
999	870713	0840	.05				SPIKE 0X1
1066	870716	1900					
1069	870720	0905		.08			SPIKE 0X1
1159	870723	1900					
1196	870803	0830	.03	.10			
1230	870804	0845					SPIKE 0X1

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN ROCK CREEK AT TIFFIN, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE UG/L	ALACHLOR UG/L	METOLACHLOR UG/L	METRIBUZIN UG/L	BUTYALTE UG/L	TERBUFOS UG/L	CHLORPYRIFOS UG/L	TREFLAN UG/L	EPTC UG/L	PHORATE UG/L
1220	870806	1900	.48									
1256	870817	0840	.28			.37						
1273	871005	0900										
1295	871019	0900				.31						
1302	871102	0850	.11						.11 .04			.12
1362	871130	0900										
1395	871214	0830	.45			.92			.04 .04			
1404	880111	0855	.20									

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN ROCK CREEK AT TIFFIN, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONOFOS UG/L	NOTES
1220	870806	1900					
1256	870817	0840	.02				SPIKE OX1
1273	871005	0900					
1295	871019	0900					
1302	871102	0850					SPIKE OX1
1362	871130	0900					
1395	871214	0830					SPIKE OX1
1404	880111	0855					

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN LOST CREEK TRIBUTARY AT DEFIANCE, OHIO IN 1987.

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CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE UG/L	ALACHLOR UG/L	METOLACHLOR UG/L	METRIBUZIN UG/L	BUTYLATE UG/L	TERBUFOS UG/L	CHLORPYRIFOS UG/L	TREFLAN UG/L	EPTC UG/L	PHORATE UG/L
90	870202	1245			2.11							
99	870209	1210	.57						.04			
101	870309	1210										
113	870330	1215	1.60	.18					.02			
117	870406	1235	.40									
138	870420	1230	.43						.03			
176	870502	1300										
178	870502	1900	8.31	4.00	5.13	.06			.02			
179	870503	0100	8.53	4.42	5.57							
180	870503	0700	10.60	5.87	2.17				.02			
181	870503	1300	30.53	8.88	9.59							
182	870503	1900	34.02	13.35	9.02							
183	870504	0100	28.67	7.73	7.99							
184	870504	0700	19.17	4.19	6.87							
185	870504	1230	14.23	3.11	6.03							
191	870504	1300	15.19	3.66	6.86							
192	870504	1900	13.90	3.15	6.54							
193	870505	0100	13.48	2.89	6.07							
194	870505	0700	13.34	2.87	6.06	.09			.08			.02
195	870505	1300	9.11	1.58	4.57							
196	870507	1900	3.19	.29	.68							
186	870511	1215	1.88	.18	.38				.04			
261	870514	0100	6.63	.35	.27							
262	870515	0100	.68	.63	.48				.05			
271	870518	1200	1.97	.45	.22							
310	870518	1300	7.08	23.35	1.64	2.66						
311	870518	1900	19.15	16.68	17.93	2.20						
312	870519	0100	21.09	22.89	18.46	4.51					.08	
313	870519	0700	14.87	18.55	20.83	5.20						
315	870519	1300	13.72	14.88	21.09	5.56						
316	870519	1900	14.50	15.01	21.77	4.88						
317	870520	0100	11.62	8.48	16.13	3.59						
318	870520	1300	9.90	8.89	14.68	3.52						
319	870521	0100	8.32	4.10	11.81	1.92						
321	870521	1300	8.07	3.82	10.82	1.64						

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PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN LOST CREEK TRIBUTARY AT DEFIANCE, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONOFOS UG/L	NOTES
90	870202	1245				6.49	
99	870209	1210		.13	.01	.06	
101	870309	1210					
113	870330	1215				.21	
117	870406	1235			.02		SPIKE 0X1
138	870420	1230		.09		.09	SPLIT 0
176	870502	1300	1.26			*	
178	870502	1900	3.81	.27	.07	*	
179	870503	0100	4.18	.25	.06	*	
180	870503	0700	2.32	.13	.06	*	
181	870503	1300	10.49	.28	.18	*	
182	870503	1900	9.50	.31	.23	*	
183	870504	0100	10.93	.29	.27	*	
184	870504	0700	9.67	.21	.25	*	
185	870504	1230	9.05	.16	.23	*	
191	870504	1300	12.50	.20	.31	2.75	
192	870504	1900	14.81	.19	.29	2.39	
193	870505	0100	15.60	.17	.34	2.31	
194	870505	0700	15.18	.21	.37	2.27	
195	870505	1300	13.89	.13	.42	1.33	
196	870507	1900	2.92	.09	.42	.46	
186	870511	1215	29.54		.26	.76	SPIKE 0X1
261	870514	0100	.61		.14	.98	
262	870515	0100	.10		.04		
271	870518	1200	.35		.29	.25	
310	870518	1300	.73	.06	1.16	.77	
311	870518	1900	11.91	.40	.31	4.15	
312	870519	0100	8.48	.31	.18	3.81	
313	870519	0700	16.37	.28	.16	2.38	
315	870519	1300	15.95	.21	.12	2.18	
316	870519	1900	14.96	.24	.14	2.16	
317	870520	0100	10.94	.26	.13	1.71	
318	870520	1300	10.24	.32	.23	1.02	
319	870521	0100	8.46	.26	.21	.98	
321	870521	1300	6.78	.27	.24	.83	

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PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN LOST CREEK TRIBUTARY AT DEFIANCE, OHIO IN 1987.

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CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE UG/L	ALACHLOR UG/L	METOLACHLOR UG/L	METRIBUZIN UG/L	BUTYLATE UG/L	TERBUFOS UG/L	CHLORPYRIFOS UG/L	TREFLAN UG/L	EPTC UG/L	PHORATE UG/L
322	870522	1300	5.77	1.82	5.09	.76						
323	870523	1300	4.15	1.21	2.93	.46						
324	870526	1150	1.67	.46	1.18	.20						
351	870529	0700	1.84	.39	1.49	.19						
352	870529	1300	26.26	10.37	4.29	.35				.12		
371	870601	1300	4.75	2.02	2.84	.67		.03	.18	.18		.03
477	870601	1900	27.46	9.63	5.14	.85						
478	870602	1900	18.35	4.09	4.82	.45						
479	870604	1900	15.36	2.28	4.49	.29						
480	870608	1200	4.53	.50	1.58							
588	870611	1900	3.28	.52	1.11							
581	870615	1135	2.04	.24	.83							
758	870621	0100										
755	870621	0700	31.62	17.29	53.69	5.61			.05			.02
756	870621	1300	54.10	26.58	70.08	13.86			.01	1.66		.05
757	870621	1900	60.00	27.28	33.29	16.40			.03			.04
759	870622	0700	60.24	17.36	25.45	15.28			.01			.02

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN LOST CREEK TRIBUTARY AT DEFIANCE, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONOFOS UG/L	NOTES
322	870522	1300	4.12	.21	.22	.66	
323	870523	1300	2.64	.17	.22	.31	
324	870526	1150	1.32	.09	.30	.23	
351	870529	0700	.78		2.79	.08	
352	870529	1300	5.08	.16	5.80	1.30	
371	870601	1300	.90	.22	3.33	.24	SPIKE OX1
477	870601	1900	10.27	.24	1.07	2.95	
478	870602	1900	9.13	.30	.39	2.37	
479	870604	1900	4.91	.25	.57		
480	870608	1200	1.71	.13	.39		
588	870611	1900	1.48	.50	1.47	1.09	
581	870615	1135	.66	.08		.11	SPIKE OX1
758	870621	0100					
755	870621	0700	.05	.73	.25	1.89	
756	870621	1300	1.94	.71	.43	6.98	
757	870621	1900	3.37	1.02	.54	8.83	
759	870622	0700	3.53	.93	.46	7.60	

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN LOST CREEK TRIBUTARY AT DEFIANCE, OHIO IN 1987.

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CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE UG/L	ALACHLOR UG/L	METOLACHLOR UG/L	METRIBUZIN UG/L	BUTYLATE UG/L	TERBUFOS UG/L	CHLORPYRIFOS UG/L	TREFLAN UG/L	EPTC UG/L	PHORATE UG/L
720	870622	1215	42.92	11.74	18.92	9.12			.02	.71		.03
840	870622	1900	23.34	5.55	18.78	5.15			.05			.04
841	870623	0100	20.60	8.20	25.46	6.78			.04			
842	870623	0700	22.21	7.36	18.37	7.12				.46		
843	870623	1900	21.61	4.37	13.92	4.82						.03
844	870626	1300	10.82	.73	6.43	1.75						
845	870629	1145	6.28	.90	4.49	.85						
898	870630	1900	5.79	1.47	10.32	1.05						
899	870701	0100	9.83	2.40	8.71	1.65						
900	870701	0700	10.50	1.45	6.64	1.88						
901	870701	1900	12.17	1.16	6.66	1.81						
902	870702	0700	10.26	.53	6.31	1.51				.36		
904	870702	1900	12.82	.94	9.90	2.92			.02			
905	870704	0100	9.94	2.16	8.17	1.88						
906	870704	0700	8.60	2.10	8.29	1.61						
910	870704	1900	9.45	.80	5.88	1.46						
911	870705	0700	9.43	.77	4.70	1.31						
912	870705	1900	7.97	.37	4.00	.93						
913	870706	0100	7.15	1.14	4.05	.93						
915	870706	0700	8.03	1.46	5.47	2.36			.01			
917	870706	1058	8.02	.75	3.94	.97						
1018	870706	1300					.17					
1019	870706	1900	.01									
1020	870707	0100	10.00	.77	4.83							
1021	870707	0700		3.91		1.62	.12				.52	
1025	870707	1300	8.60	.84	5.01	1.21		.02				
1026	870707	1900	9.35	.40	5.08	.99						
1027	870708	0100	8.33	.55	4.80	.83		.02				
1028	870708	0700	7.45	.48	4.72							
1029	870708	1900	6.22	.33	4.04	.63						

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PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN LOST CREEK TRIBUTARY AT DEFIANCE, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONOFOS UG/L	NOTES
720	870622	1215	2.86	.64	.37	7.10	SPIKE OX1
840	870622	1900	4.55	1.24	.73	3.46	
841	870623	0100	3.09	.96	.19	1.67	
842	870623	0700	4.38	1.06	.18	3.19	
843	870623	1900	6.08	1.81	.20	4.94	
844	870626	1300	2.05	.75			
845	870629	1145	1.00	.48			FIELD REP 0
898	870630	1900			.37		
899	870701	0100	.03		.38		
900	870701	0700	.03		.55		
901	870701	1900		.78	.68		
902	870702	0700		.77	.61		
904	870702	1900	.01		1.04		
905	870704	0100			.46		
906	870704	0700			.71		
910	870704	1900			.82		
911	870705	0700			.77		
912	870705	1900		.81			
913	870706	0100	.03				
915	870706	0700			1.00		
917	870706	1058	.01		.47		FIELD REP 0
1018	870706	1300	.10				
1019	870706	1900			.05		
1020	870707	0100		.12		1.20	
1021	870707	0700	.07				
1025	870707	1300	1.37	.94			
1026	870707	1900	1.69	1.19		1.13	
1027	870708	0100	1.76			.99	
1028	870708	0700		.15	.04		
1029	870708	1900	1.13	.93			

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PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN LOST CREEK TRIBUTARY AT DEFIANCE, OHIO IN 1987.

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CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE UG/L	ALACHLOR UG/L	METOLACHLOR UG/L	METRIBUZIN UG/L	BUTYLATE UG/L	TERBUFOS UG/L	CHLORPYRIFOS UG/L	TREFLAN UG/L	EPTC UG/L	PHORATE UG/L
1030	870709	1900	4.98	.55	3.35	.63						
1032	870713	1205	2.45	.14	2.15	.30						
1155	870723	1900	4.13	.47	2.06	.30						
1157	870727	1217			.43	.14						
1197	870730	1900	1.18		.42	.14						
1198	870803	1140	.50		.13							
1229	870806	1900										
1253	870817	1155										
1275	871005	1230	.22									
1279	871019	1220	.74									
1316	871102	1225	.24	.31		.12		.01	.10			
1359	871116	1205							.07			
1386	871130	1230	.93		.61							
1392	871214	1135	.34									

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN LOST CREEK TRIBUTARY AT DEFIANCE, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONDFOS UG/L	NOTES
1030	870709	1900	.92	.74			
1032	870713	1205	.34	.36			FIELD REP 0
1155	870723	1900	.55	.18			
1157	870727	1217	.41	.15	.09		FIELD REP 0
1197	870730	1900	.17	.15			
1198	870803	1140	.14	.18			
1229	870806	1900	.02				
1253	870817	1155					SPIKE 0X1
1275	871005	1230					
1279	871019	1220					SPIKE 0X1
1316	871102	1225	.10	.76			
1359	871116	1205	.05				
1386	871130	1230		.34			
1392	871214	1135		.14			FIELD REP 0

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN THE RIVER RAISIN NEAR MONROE, MICHIGAN IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE UG/L	ALACHLOR UG/L	METOLACHLOR UG/L	METKIBUZIN UG/L	BUTYLATE UG/L	TERBUFOS UG/L	CHLORPYRIFOS UG/L	TREFLAN UG/L	EPTC UG/L	PHORATE UG/L
613	870609	1745	5.15	2.73	1.82	.39			.05			
763	870618	1745	2.02	.43	.52	.15			.11	.82		.01
830	870623	1745	6.37	2.67	2.73	1.63			.03			
788	870630	1745	5.96	1.14	1.31	.52			.05			
1041	870708	1745	2.34	.26	.80	.19			.06			
1094	870719	1745	1.00	2.39	.19	.10	.45		.11			
1261	870814	1745										
1268	870823	1900	.23									
1269	870825	1245										
1314	871103	1745	.59	.24		.11						
1357	871127	1745		.22								
1166	979726	1745	.74	.37	.14	.04						
1394	990103	1330	.27						.06			

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN THE RIVER RAISIN NEAR MONROE, MICHIGAN IN 1987

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PAGE 1

CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONOFOS UG/L	NOTES
613	870609	1745	2.31	.25	.39	.78	
763	870618	1745		.13			
830	870623	1745	1.36	.40	.16	.60	
788	870630	1745	1.26	.34	.21		
1041	870708	1745	.28	.18		.40	
1094	870719	1745		.15			
1261	870814	1745	.53	.11			
1268	870823	1900	.07				
1269	870825	1245					
1314	871103	1745	.11	.08		.25	
1357	871127	1745					
1166	979726	1745	.09		.28		
1394	990103	1330					

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN THE CUYAHOGA RIVER AT INDEPENDENCE, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	ATRAZINE UG/L	ALACHLOR UG/L	METOLACHLOR UG/L	METRIBUZIN UG/L	BUTYLATE UG/L	TERBUFOS UG/L	CHLORPYRIFOS UG/L	TREFLAN UG/L	EPTC UG/L	PHORATE UG/L
764	870622		2.33	.13	.14				.04			
829	870629		3.44	1.27	4.01	.73						
1062	870704	1300	.56		.21							
976	870706		.66		.20							
1095	870721		.39		.03				.05			
1184	870728		.60	.55	5.76		6.92	1.47		11.61	1.42	1.39
1271	870821											
1272	870831		.20									
1315	871102	1615	.49						.09			
1319	871110	1330	.08			.04			.05			
1388	871208	1230	.07						.03			
1389	871230		.08						.05			
1406	880111	1330	.09									

PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN THE CUYAHOGA RIVER AT INDEPENDENCE, OHIO IN 1987

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CID	DATE	TIME	CYANAZINE UG/L	PENDIMETHYLIN UG/L	SIMAZINE UG/L	FONOFDS UG/L	NOTES
764	870622		.44	1.35	1.41	.51	
829	870629		.23	.04			
1062	870704	1300				.28	
976	870706				.48		SPIKE OX1
1095	870721		.04		.38		
1184	870728			.36			SPIKE OX1
1271	870821						
1272	870831		.11				
1315	871102	1615	.09				
1319	871110	1330	.06				
1388	871208	1230	.09				
1389	871230						
1406	880111	1330					